
1 **Title: Warming Weakens Soil Nitrogen Stabilization Pathways Driving**
2 **Proportional Carbon Losses in Subarctic Ecosystems**

3 **Running title: Warming Weakens Soil N Stabilization**

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27 **Abstract**

28 Climate warming poses a significant threat to the nitrogen (N) and carbon (C) retention
29 capacities of subarctic ecosystems, with cascading effects on soil nutrient cycling and
30 long-term ecosystem functioning. Here, we investigated the effects sustained soil
31 warming on the temporal retention and stabilization of N in key ecosystem pools in a
32 subarctic grassland performing a ^{15}N -tracing experiment in different seasons.

33 Our results reveal that warming reduced N retention across key soil pools, with the
34 largest proportional losses occurring in the non-extractable soil fraction, a critical long-
35 term reservoir of organic matter. These losses were driven by the depletion of organic
36 compounds involved in *ex vivo* N stabilization and the weakening of *in vivo*
37 stabilization mechanisms. Warming also decreased microbial and fine root biomass,
38 limiting their ability to temporarily immobilize N during the snowmelt period, when
39 soil N retention is most critical.

40 In contrast, warming increased aboveground plant biomass and N uptake during
41 the growing season, indicating a shift in resource allocation towards aboveground
42 tissues. However, the increase in plant N uptake, both due to its magnitude (0.14% of
43 N gained $^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$) and seasonality, was insufficient to offset the loss of N retention in the
44 microbial biomass and fine roots (1.99% of N lost $^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$), and non-extractable soil pools
45 (1.7-2.6% of N lost $^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$). As a consequence, we observed coupled and proportional C
46 losses across all soil pools. These findings suggest that warming disrupts key pathways
47 of soil N stabilization, leading to the "opening" of the N cycle and proportional,
48 potentially irreversible, C losses from cold ecosystems.

49

50 **Keywords:** Soil warming, Nitrogen loss, Carbon loss, Carbon and nitrogen cycling,
51 Soil microbial biomass, High latitude ecosystems, Plant-soil interactions, ^{15}N isotope
52 tracing, Fine root biomass, Plant nitrogen uptake

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56 **Introduction**

57 Global warming accelerates soil organic matter (SOM) decomposition, resulting in
58 significant CO₂ emissions, which in turn contribute to climate change feedbacks
59 (Jenkinson et al., 1991; Davidson and Janssens, 2006). Temperatures have risen,
60 especially in high-latitude ecosystems, where a substantial portion of the Earth's soil
61 carbon (C) is stored (Tarnocai et al., 2009; Allen et al., 2018). This makes high-latitude
62 cold soils potentially significant contributors to rising atmospheric CO₂ levels
63 (McGuire et al. 2009). However, the extent of this contribution remains uncertain due
64 to the complexity of plant-soil microbial interactions and nutrient cycling
65 (Friedlingstein et al., 2006; Bradford et al., 2016).

66 The coupling between the C and nitrogen (N) cycles is particularly strong in high-
67 latitude ecosystems, where slow organic matter decomposition limits the release of
68 available N for plants (Schimel and Bennett, 2004; Todd-Brown et al., 2013). Rising
69 temperatures are expected to accelerate SOM decomposition, alleviating plant N
70 limitations in northern ecosystems (Dormann and Woodin, 2002; Wu et al., 2011;
71 Natali et al., 2012). This increased N availability, coupled with longer growing seasons,
72 could enhance plant productivity and C inputs to the soil (Piao et al., 2007), potentially
73 offsetting soil C losses due to warming (Melillo et al., 2002; IPCC, 2013; Sistla et al.,
74 2013). However, responses of microbial N mineralization and plant N uptake to
75 warming may differ (Beier et al., 2008), leading to asynchronies or imbalances between
76 the fluxes of N release and uptake (Salmon et al., 2018; Lacroix et al. 2022). The
77 resilience of soil C stocks to warming thus depends on soil nutrient retention and on the
78 capacity of plant productivity to benefit from alleviated nutrient limitations.

79 Microbial biomass plays a crucial role in retaining soil N in low-productivity
80 ecosystems like high latitudes (Haugwitz et al., 2011; Xu et al., 2013; Marañón-Jiménez
81 et al., 2019). This N pool has high turnover rates compared to other soil nutrient
82 fractions, making it a dynamic component of soil nutrient fluxes (Bardgett et al., 2003;
83 Haugwitz et al., 2011). Seasonal oscillations of microbial biomass are consequence of
84 this fast microbial turnover (Wardle, 1998; Turner and Henry, 2010). In cold soils,
85 microbial biomass typically peaks at the end of winter, followed by a release of soil

86 nutrients (Kuhnert et al., 2012; Edwards and Jefferies, 2013; Schnecker et al., 2023).
87 Therefore, microbial biomass can serve as a short-term soil N reservoir during periods
88 of low plant productivity and N uptake, such as the cold winters with short photoperiods
89 at high latitudes, whereas microbial turnover and subsequent release of N into the plant-
90 soil system can represent the largest annual flux of available N for plants during the
91 growing season (Lipson et al., 2000; Bardgett et al., 2003). The soil microbial biomass
92 N pool is then crucial to maintain a soil N reservoir during relatively long winter periods
93 and regulate soil N availability across seasons (Jonasson et al., 1996; Groffman et al.,
94 2011; Kaiser et al., 2011).

95 Climate warming may disrupt the coupling between microbial N mineralization and
96 plant N uptake, potentially leading to N losses in cold ecosystems (Dawes et al., 2017;
97 Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2019). Warming can deplete the labile soil C pool and
98 exacerbate microbial C limitation for growth if the increased microbial activity and
99 respiration are not offset by higher vegetation productivity and C inputs (Sullivan et al.,
100 2020). Winter warming in particular, can impact negatively the soil microbial N
101 reservoir (Edwards and Jefferies, 2013), affecting the timing and magnitude of the
102 posterior N release to the soil. In addition, pulses of available N during thawing events,
103 when plant N uptake is low, can lead to denitrification and N leaching from high-
104 latitude ecosystems (Turner and Henry, 2010; Salmon et al., 2018). Therefore, repeated
105 cycles of low microbial N immobilization during warm winters may deplete N from
106 high-latitude soils, limiting plant N availability, productivity, and the ability of
107 vegetation to offset soil C losses caused by warming (Salmon et al., 2018; Harms et al.
108 2019; Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2019).

109 There is limited information on potential asynchronies or imbalances in N
110 biogeochemical processes within the soil-plant continuum mediated by warming,
111 despite its crucial role in the resilience of soil C stocks at high latitudes. Understanding
112 these interactions is essential for predicting the long-term stability of soil C in response
113 to climate change. In addition, climate projections estimate a rise in global mean
114 temperatures of 1.4°C to 4.4°C, with disproportionately strong warming at northern
115 latitudes (IPCC, 2023). While most field experiments simulate moderate warming,

116 there remains a critical knowledge gap regarding the impacts of extreme warming,
117 which may become increasingly relevant under future climate trajectories (IPCC,
118 2023). Here, we investigate the effects of a broad gradient of soil warming intensities,
119 ranging from ambient to +12 °C, which includes both projected and extreme warming
120 levels (Sigurdsson et al., 2016). Studying this wide range of warming intensities enables
121 us to detect non-linearities, critical thresholds and identify robust ecological responses
122 applicable to various climate scenarios. Geothermal gradients provide a unique
123 opportunity to address these gaps, as they offer a natural, continuous, and long-term
124 warming treatment across a wide range of temperatures without introducing
125 experimental artifacts or perturbations. For these reasons, we conducted an isotope
126 tracing experiment in subarctic grasslands at different seasons, using a mixture of ¹⁵N-
127 labeled amino acids applied along decade-old natural soil geothermal gradients. Two
128 weeks after each seasonal tracing campaign, we measured the remaining N and ¹⁵N
129 pools in roots, aboveground vegetation, soil, and microbial biomass.

130 We hypothesized that warming would cause an imbalance in N biogeochemical
131 processes, where rising temperatures reduce microbial biomass, thus diminishing the
132 soil capacity to retain N, particularly during winter periods. This would contribute to
133 ecosystem N losses and lower N availability for plant productivity. We also expected a
134 N biogeochemical asynchrony, where winter soil N losses are not compensated by
135 increased plant productivity and N uptake during the warmer growing seasons.
136 Consequently, this would result in overall N losses in the subarctic ecosystem under a
137 warmer climate. Lower soil N availability would imply a reduced vegetation
138 productivity in cold ecosystems, weakening the capacity of these ecosystems to
139 counteract warming-induced soil C losses and causing stoichiometrically equivalent
140 soil C losses.

141

142 **Materials and Methods**

143 *Study Site*

144 Samples were collected from an unmanaged grassland located near the village of
145 Hveragerði in southwest Iceland (64°00'01"N, 21°11'09"W; 83–168 m a.s.l.). The study

146 site is part of the ForHot research infrastructure (www.forhot.is) and is described in
147 detail by Sigurdsson et al. (2016). Between 2003 and 2015, the mean annual
148 temperature, precipitation and wind speed were 5.2°C, 1457 mm and 6.6 m s⁻¹,
149 respectively, according to records from the Eyrarbakki synoptic station, located 9 km
150 south of the site (Icelandic Meteorological Office). The warmest month is July, with a
151 mean temperature of 12.2°C, while the coldest month is December, averaging -0.1°C.
152 The growing season typically spans from late May to late August. Although snow cover
153 is generally intermittent due to the region's mild oceanic climate, soils usually freeze
154 for at least several weeks during mid-winter (Sigurdsson et al., 2016).

155 Vegetation in the study sites include dominant species adapted to withstand cold
156 conditions and regrow rapidly when favorable conditions return, giving them a
157 competitive advantage (Chapin et al., 1986; Starr et al., 2003; Larsen et al., 2012).
158 Among these species is *Agrostis capillaris*, a perennial grass with short-lived
159 aboveground parts that annually regrow from underground stems or rhizomes. These
160 structures store energy and nutrients, supporting new growth each spring. *Ranunculus*
161 *acris* is another perennial herb that can maintain a rosette of leaves close to the ground
162 throughout the winter. Additionally, *Equisetum pratense* is a perennial horsetail that
163 maintains green aboveground shoots during winter. There are no N-fixing plant species
164 in the study sites (Meynzer, 2017). The soil is classified as Silandic Andosol (IUSS
165 Working Group WRB, 2015) with a fine silt loam texture, exhibiting strong binding
166 strength, high water-holding capacity and soil pH values ranging from 5.43 to 6.15. The
167 estimated annual atmospheric deposition rate in the study sites is 1.3-1.4 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹
168 (Gislason et al., 1996; Leblans et al., 2014).

169 In 2008, a magnitude 6.3 earthquake disrupted the local geothermal system,
170 causing hot groundwater to heat the underlying bedrock and rise through newly formed
171 faults in the soil crust. This led to the development of geothermal bedrock channels,
172 with soil temperatures highest near the faults and decreasing with distance, thereby
173 creating natural gradients of soil warming across previously unaffected areas
174 (Halldórsson & Sigbjörnsson, 2009). This gradients range from ambient conditions to
175 plots experiencing substantial geothermal heating (>20°C and beyond), offering a

176 unique opportunity to study terrestrial ecosystem responses across a broad spectrum of
177 long-term soil warming intensities. Importantly, the warming remains relatively stable
178 over time and mirrors the seasonal cycle of soil temperature observed in ambient plots.
179 Furthermore, soil chemical analyses confirmed the absence of geothermal
180 contamination (e.g., no elevated exchangeable sulfur) at the study sites (Sigurdsson et
181 al., 2016).

182

183 *Experimental Design*

184 Plots measuring 0.5 m × 0.5 m were established in homogeneous areas with similar
185 exposure, plant communities, and soil types, spanning soil temperature gradients from
186 ambient to +12 °C above ambient (n = 20 plots). The selected plots were distributed
187 across two clusters of approximately 1000 m² each, centered around two main
188 geothermal hot spots located about 700 m apart. To ensure balanced representation
189 across the entire warming range, plots were initially selected based on instantaneous
190 differences between soil temperature at potential warmed locations and paired ambient
191 reference plots. This approach allowed us to achieve an even distribution of soil
192 temperatures along the gradient. We limited our selection to plots with warming up to
193 +12 °C, as higher temperatures showed clear signs of vegetation die-off, indicating
194 collapse of the plant community, and were therefore considered beyond the ecologically
195 relevant range for assessing climate warming effects. Once the plots were established,
196 soil temperature at 10 cm depth was continuously monitored in each plot using TidbiT
197 v2 HOBO Data Loggers (Onset Computer Corporation, Bourne, USA), and these data
198 were used to calculate the warming intensity experienced at each plot.

199 A PVC collar of 13 cm diameter and 10 cm length was inserted in the soil of each
200 plot, leaving 1 cm of headspace. These collars served to demarcate the soil area for
201 isotope tracing, and they were open cylinders at the upper and lower ends to allow
202 natural water flow and prevent lateral contamination. In July 2018, soil cores up to
203 10 cm of mineral soil (corer ø=5.12 cm) were taken within each subplot and soil bulk
204 density was determined according to the approach described in detail Verbrigghe et al.
205 (2022).

206

207 *Isotope tracing and field sampling*

208 Isotope tracing was conducted at four dates under contrasting seasonal conditions: in
209 summer (August 2017), autumn (November 2017), during the snowmelt period in the
210 colder plots (April 2018), and in spring (June 2018). During each tracing campaign, 15
211 ml of a 5mM ¹⁵N-algal amino acid mixture (referred to as ¹⁵N-Aa) with 98% atom
212 enrichment (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc., UK) was injected into the soil
213 within each PVC collar using a syringe with a 7 cm needle. An organic source of ¹⁵N
214 was chosen as a N tracer since organic N represents about 99.9% of the total N and
215 69.9% of the total dissolved N in these soils (Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2019). The ¹⁵N-
216 labeled algal amino acid mixture used in this study contained a broad spectrum of 17
217 amino acids that ranged widely in chemical properties, including molecular weight,
218 C:N ratio, average net charge, hydrophobicity, and polarity. Notably, eight of the most
219 abundant and commonly detected amino acids in high-latitude soils—aspartic acid,
220 glutamic acid, serine, glycine, threonine, alanine, histidine and arginine (Weintraub &
221 Schimel, 2005; Kielland, 1995; Andresen et al., 2022)—accounted for approximately
222 56.6% of the total molar composition of the solution. These compounds are not only
223 ubiquitous in the free amino acid pool of cold soils, but have also been widely shown
224 to be preferentially taken up by soil microbes and plants across a variety of boreal,
225 subarctic, and alpine ecosystems (Ravn et al. 2017; Månsson et al. 2014; Nordin et
226 al. 2004; Wilkinson et al., 2014). The inclusion of these key amino acids ensures that
227 the labeling solution reflects the composition of biologically relevant organic N sources
228 commonly available in these ecosystems.

229 To ensure uniform distribution over the upper 7 cm of soil (the needle length), 1 ml
230 of the ¹⁵N-Aa solution was injected at 15 evenly spaced points within the collars using
231 a grid placed over the soil surface. We also used a manual syringe injection method
232 adapted for vertical delivery. A stopper was fixed at the top of the syringe plunger to
233 control the injection volume, and the barrel of the syringe was gradually retracted
234 upward during injection (7-0 cm depth). This controlled motion ensured a
235 homogeneous vertical distribution of the solution within the targeted soil layer. The

236 amount of N injected in the ^{15}N -Aa solution represented an average of 15.1% of total
237 dissolved N and 46.3% of the total soil free amino acids, but only a 1.48% of the daily
238 amino acid production through gross protein depolymerization.

239 Previous studies in the same study plots showed that natural abundance of the ^{15}N
240 isotope in bulk soil was not significantly affected by soil warming ($\delta^{15}\text{N}=-$
241 $0.25\pm 0.17\%$, $P=0.475$). For this reason, deionized water was injected similarly into five
242 additional collars located at ambient temperatures to account for the natural abundance
243 of ^{15}N . The 15 ml of ^{15}N -Aa solution only caused an increase of 5.5% on the soil water
244 content inside the collars.

245 Two weeks after the ^{15}N tracing, all soil and vegetation growing within each collar
246 were sampled destructively. For that, the soil surrounding one side of the collar was
247 first excavated with a shovel to facilitate the removal of the entire PVC collar content,
248 and then the entire PVC collar containing soil and vegetation was carefully extracted
249 using a trowel to prevent soil loss from the collar bottom. These PVC collars, each
250 containing soil and vegetation, were placed in individual plastic bags and transported
251 to the laboratory.

252

253 *Sample processing*

254 Aboveground vegetation within the collars was cut at ground level, separated into green
255 and litter and senescent plant material (Green and Senescent aboveground vegetation,
256 hereafter), and rinsed with deionized water. The soil core, including roots and stones,
257 was then removed from the PVC collar. All fresh soil within each core was sieved
258 through a 2 mm mesh, weighed, and stored at 4 °C for subsequent analyses. Roots were
259 meticulously separated from the soil, cleaned with deionized water, and sorted into fine
260 roots (<2mm) and coarse roots (>2mm) and rhizomes (Fine roots and Coarse roots and
261 rhizomes). All plant material from each core, including sorted aboveground plant
262 material and roots, was oven-dried at 60 °C for 48 hours, weighed, and ground using a
263 ball mill. Similarly, a 5 g soil subsample from each collar was dried in an oven at 60 °C
264 for 48 hours, then weighed and ground (Bulk soil).

265 All tools and materials used for sample processing and sorting were cleaned and
266 washed with acetone between samples to prevent cross-isotopic contamination.
267 Samples injected with deionized water were processed using a separate set of tools and
268 materials to avoid contamination by labeled samples.

269

270 *Sample analyses*

271 Dried, ground, and homogenized soil and plant materials from each sorted plant pool
272 (Green and Senescent aboveground vegetation, Fine roots, Coarse roots and rhizomes,
273 and Bulk soil) were analyzed for total organic C, total N and ^{15}N using an elemental
274 analyzer (Carlo Erba 1110, CE Instruments, Wigan, UK) coupled to an isotope-ratio
275 mass spectrometer (Finnigan MAT DeltaPlus; Fisher Scientific, Vienna, Austria) via a
276 ConFlo III interface (Thermo Fisher, Waltham, EEUU). Aliquots of 2 grams of
277 homogenized fresh soil subsamples were extracted using 0.5 M K_2SO_4 and analyzed for
278 dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and total dissolved nitrogen (TDN) (Dissolved soil
279 fraction) with a TOC/TN analyzer (TOC-VCPH/CPN/TNM-1, Shimadzu, Austria).
280 Microbial C and microbial N (Soil microbial biomass) were calculated from the
281 difference between DOC and TDN in non-fumigated and fumigated soil samples using
282 the chloroform fumigation-extraction method (Jenkinson and Powlson, 1976). The ^{15}N
283 isotopic composition of the dissolved soil fraction and microbial biomass were also
284 determined. For this, we oxidized aliquots of the respective fumigated and non-
285 fumigated 0.5 M K_2SO_4 extract solutions with alkaline persulfate solution ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ with
286 H_3BO_3) to convert organic N compounds and NH_4 to NO_3 (Cabrera and Beare, 1993;
287 Doyle et al., 2004). Subsequently, NO_3 was converted to NO_2 with vanadium (III)
288 chloride (VCl_3) under acidic conditions, and NO_2 was further reduced to N_2O by sodium
289 azide (NaN_3) (Lachouani et al., 2010). Measurements of N_2O concentrations and
290 isotopic compositions were done by PT-IRMS, using a Gasbench II headspace analyzer
291 (Thermo Fisher, Bremen, Germany) with a cryo-focusing unit, coupled to a Finnigan
292 Delta V Advantage IRMS (Thermo Fisher, Bremen, Germany) as outlined in Lachouani
293 et al. (2010). The ^{15}N in atom percent (at%) in the microbial biomass ($^{15}\text{N}_{\text{micro}}$) was
294 calculated as:

295
$$^{15}\text{N}_{\text{micro}} = (^{15}\text{N}_{\text{F}} * \text{TDN}_{\text{F}} - ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NF}} * \text{TDN}_{\text{NF}}) / \text{microbial N} \quad (1)$$

296 where $^{15}\text{N}_{\text{F}}$ and $^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NF}}$ are the ^{15}N content in atom percent in the extracts of the
 297 fumigated and non-fumigated samples, respectively, and TN_{F} and TN_{NF} are the total
 298 dissolved nitrogen in fumigated and non-fumigated samples, respectively. The
 299 concentrations in the microbial fraction presented here were not corrected for extraction
 300 efficiency.

301 The ^{15}N isotopic enrichment (at%) of labeled samples ($^{15}\text{N}_{\text{labeled}}$) was corrected by
 302 the ^{15}N isotopic enrichment of non-labeled samples ($^{15}\text{N}_{\text{non-labeled}}$) to calculate the atom
 303 percent excess of each sample (*APE*) as:

304
$$\text{APE} (\%) = ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{labeled}} - ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{non-labeled}}$$

 305 (2)

306 All fractions are presented relative to soil dry mass.

307

308 *Data analyses*

309 The amount of added ^{15}N remaining in each pool two weeks after the tracer addition
 310 was calculated using the following equations:

311
$$^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}} (\%) = \frac{\text{APE} * \text{TN} * \frac{\text{Pa}^{15}\text{N}}{\text{Pa}^{14}\text{N}}}{^{15}\text{N}_{\text{add}}} * 100 \quad (3)$$

312 where *APE* is the atom percent excess of each sample, *TN* is the total N stock in
 313 the correspondent pool, Pa^{15}N and Pa^{14}N are the atomic weights of ^{15}N and ^{14}N ,
 314 respectively, and $^{15}\text{N}_{\text{add}}$ is a constant, representing the ^{15}N injected in each collar per
 315 square meter (84.757 mg/m²). Then, percentage of added ^{15}N remaining in the non-
 316 extractable soil fraction was calculated as:

317
$$^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{non-extractable}}} (\%) = ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{bulk soil}}} - ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{microbes}}} - ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{dissolved}}} \quad (4)$$

318 where $^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{bulk soil}}}$, $^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{microbes}}}$, $^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{dissolved}}}$ are the
 319 percentages of added ^{15}N recovered in the bulk soil, soil microbial biomass and in the
 320 dissolved soil fraction, respectively. We also calculated the percentage of added ^{15}N
 321 that was not recovered from the sampled ecosystem pools as:

322
$$^{15}\text{N}_{\text{lost}} = 100 - ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{bulk soil}}} - ^{15}\text{N}_{\text{remaining}_{\text{vegetation}}} \quad (5)$$

324 where $^{15}N_{remaining_{vegetation}}$ is the percentage of added ^{15}N recovered in all
325 vegetation pools (Green and Senescent aboveground vegetation, Fine roots and Coarse
326 roots and rhizomes).

327 The effects of soil warming, seasons, and their interaction on the C and N stocks,
328 C:N ratios and the ^{15}N enrichment of soil and vegetation pools were analyzed using
329 linear models, with soil warming as continuous independent variable, seasons as factor
330 and their interaction. When significant, differences among seasons were further tested
331 by post hoc tests with Sidak corrections for multiple testing while accounting for the
332 effects of warming. Differences in C:N ratios between soil microbes and the dissolved
333 soil fraction within seasons were further tested using one-way ANOVAs.

334 Differences in the effect of soil warming among the C and N stocks of different
335 soil pools (Bulk soil, Soil microbes, and Dissolved soil fraction; Bulk soil, Fine roots
336 and Coarse roots) were analyzed using robust linear models (RLM) on previously
337 standardized soil variables. Soil warming was included as a continuous independent
338 variable, along with the interaction term between soil warming and the pool variable.
339 Heteroskedasticity-consistent standard errors were used to evaluate the significance of
340 the effects. A significant interaction term would indicate that soil warming has a
341 differential effect on the C and N stocks of the different soil pools.

342 The effect of seasons was tested on the percentage of ^{15}N remaining in each pool
343 at the ambient temperature plots using one-way ANOVAs, and differences among
344 seasons were further tested by post hoc tests with Sidak corrections for multiple testing.
345 Then, the effect of soil warming was also tested for each pool and season separately
346 using linear models and generalized linear models from quasibinomial family,
347 including soil warming as continuous independent variable.

348 To ensure the validity of the linear models, the residuals were tested for normality
349 and homoscedasticity. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess whether the residuals
350 followed a normal distribution, and the Breusch-Pagan (linear regression models) or
351 Levene tests (ANOVAs) were used to check for homoscedasticity. When necessary,
352 Box-Cox transformations were applied to dependent variables prior to model fitting to
353 meet the assumptions of parametric models. The optimal transformation parameter (λ)

354 was estimated for each response variable using the `boxcox()` function from the MASS
355 package in R (Venables and Ripley, 2002). Because λ values varied across variables, a
356 summary of the applied transformations is provided in Table S1. All models were
357 interpreted on the transformed scale. We note that non-linear λ values imply non-linear
358 relationships between predictors and responses. All statistical analyses were conducted
359 using R (version 4.4.1). The results are presented as means \pm standard errors.

360

361 **Results**

362 *Warming and seasonal effects on C and N pools*

363 In this subarctic grassland, total N stocks, including all considered ecosystem pools at
364 ambient soil temperatures, were 174.92 ± 0.86 g m⁻². The non-extractable soil N fraction
365 was the largest pool (161.9 g m⁻² and 92.5% of the N pools), followed by fine roots (3.7
366 g m⁻² and 2.1%) and senescent aboveground vegetation (3.2 g m⁻² and 1.8%). Soil
367 microbial biomass (2.6 g m⁻² and 1.5%), the coarse roots and rhizomes (1.3 g m⁻² and
368 0.7%) and the dissolved soil fraction (1.17 g m⁻² and 0.7%) followed in magnitude,
369 while the smallest N pools were represented by the green aboveground vegetation (1.1
370 g m⁻² and 0.6%).

371 Key soil C and N stocks exhibited consistent declines along the soil temperature
372 gradient across seasons (Fig. 1). Soil organic carbon (SOC) and total soil nitrogen (TN)
373 stocks decreased with warming ($P < 0.001$, Fig. 1a and b) in the same proportion,
374 maintaining a constant soil C:N ratio despite temperature variation (Fig. 1c). Similarly,
375 microbial biomass and dissolved C and N stocks also decreased consistently in response
376 to temperature increases ($P < 0.001$, Fig 1d, e, g and h), leading to constant microbial
377 biomass and dissolved C:N ratios along the soil temperature gradient (Fig. 1i). The rates
378 of decline of C and N stocks in bulk soil, microbial biomass and dissolved soil fractions
379 were similar, as indicated by the lack of significant interaction between warming and
380 the standardized soil variables (Fig. 1f). Nonetheless, C:N ratios of microbial biomass
381 were larger than the C:N ratios of the dissolved soil fraction during autumn and spring
382 (Fig. 1i).

383 Key vegetation C and N stocks also changed with soil warming consistently across
384 seasons (Fig. 2). Root C and N stocks, both from fine roots, coarse roots and rhizomes,
385 declined with soil warming ($P>0.02$, Fig. 2a, b, d, e). Nonetheless, the C content in fine
386 roots decreased more than its N content, causing a consistent decrease in fine roots C:N
387 ratios with warming across seasons (Fig. 2c), where values were lower in spring and
388 snowmelt. By contrast, C and N stocks in green aboveground vegetation increased
389 proportionally and consistently with soil warming across seasons ($P<0.02$, Fig. 2g and
390 h), without changes in C:N ratios along the warming gradient (Warming: $P=0.573$,
391 Season: $P=0.071$, Warming x Season: $P=0.771$). Consequently, root:shoot ratios
392 declined with soil warming consistently across seasons (Warming: $P<0.001$, Season:
393 $P=0.579$, Warming x Season: $P=0.270$). The rate of decline of bulk soil C stocks was
394 similar to the one of fine roots C stocks, as indicated by the lack of significant
395 interaction between warming and the standardized soil variables ($P=0.070$), but differed
396 from fine roots N stocks (Warming x Variable: $P=0.041$) and from the C and N stocks
397 in coarse roots and rhizomes (Warming x Variable: $P=0.028$ and $P<0.001$, respectively)
398 (Fig. 2i). Carbon and N stocks in senescent aboveground vegetation were not affected
399 by soil warming ($P>0.21$), but were higher in summer and autumn ($P<0.001$).

400

401 *Warming and seasonal effects on ^{15}N pools recovered after tracing*

402 In plots at ambient temperatures, 90.1% to 77.4% of the added ^{15}N in the algal amino-
403 acid mixture was recovered from either the vegetation or the upper 9 cm of soil (the
404 depth of the PVC collar insertion), although there were no significant differences
405 among seasons. A 10.1% to 22.6% of the added ^{15}N was recovered in the soil microbial
406 biomass pool, and 2.1% to 10.8% was recovered from fine roots, with the highest
407 recoveries during snowmelt and the lowest in spring ($P=0.005$ for soil microbes,
408 $P=0.013$ for fine roots, Fig. 3). On the contrary, the ^{15}N recovered from the dissolved
409 soil fraction was highest in spring (ca. 6.4%) and lowest in autumn (ca. 1.6%, $P=0.033$).
410 An important ^{15}N portion (45.6% to 67.5%) was also recovered from the non-
411 extractable soil fraction, with some effect of seasons ($P=0.040$) but without significant
412 pairwise differences after Sidak post-hoc correction. Senescent aboveground

413 vegetation, coarse roots and rhizomes, and green aboveground vegetation contained
414 0.7-2.4%, 0.3-2.3% and 0.1-1.1% of the added ^{15}N , respectively.

415 Soil temperatures affected the ^{15}N recovered from soil and vegetation pools (Fig.
416 4). The decline in the ^{15}N recovered in the non-extractable soil pool, despite being
417 significant only for autumn, summer, and the snowmelt period, had the highest
418 influence on the global ^{15}N retention, due to his large magnitude compared to the other
419 ecosystem pools considered. As a result, N losses detected in this pool accounted for
420 1.7%-2.6% of the total N loss per degree $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of warming. Nonetheless, the decrease in
421 ^{15}N pool recovered in the soil microbial biomass and fine roots during the snowmelt
422 period ($P=0.013$ and $P=0.002$, respectively) together accounted for $2.0\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ of the N
423 loss during this period. By contrast, soil warming increased the ^{15}N pool retained by
424 green aboveground vegetation in spring ($0.17\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $P=0.016$) and summer ($0.12\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$,
425 $P=0.001$), as well as the ^{15}N recovered in senescent aboveground vegetation during
426 summer ($0.15\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $P=0.002$), which contributed to compensate the N loss in the
427 dissolved soil fraction during these seasons (spring: $0.42\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $P=0.022$; summer:
428 $0.22\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $P=0.003$).

429

430 *Warming and seasonal effects on the ^{15}N enrichment of ecosystem pools after tracing*

431 Soil microbial biomass was the ecosystem reservoir with highest ^{15}N enrichment two
432 weeks after the tracer addition, followed by the fine roots, coarse roots and green leaves.
433 Bulk soil and the senescent above ground vegetation were the ecosystem pools with the
434 lowest ^{15}N enrichment (Fig. 5). While the ^{15}N enrichment of the bulk soil was not
435 affected by soil warming or seasons (Fig. 6a), the ^{15}N enrichment of the soil microbial
436 biomass, dissolved soil fraction and fine roots pools were affected only by seasons (Fig.
437 6b, c and d), where soil microbes and fine roots were more enriched in ^{15}N during the
438 snowmelt period and the dissolved soil fraction during the spring and snowmelt period.
439 The ^{15}N enrichment of green and senescent aboveground vegetation increased with soil
440 warming and showed the lowest values in autumn (Fig 6e and f).

441

442 **Discussion**

443 We hypothesized that soil warming disrupts the balance between microbial N
444 mineralization and plant N uptake, causing N losses from the plant-soil system. Our
445 findings reveal that warming compromises the stabilization of N in the non-extractable
446 soil organic matter fraction, a key reservoir of long-term soil fertility. Warming also
447 reduces the capacity of microbial biomass and fine roots to temporarily store N during
448 cold periods, exacerbating N losses when plant uptake is limited. Warming-induced N
449 losses from ecosystems have critical implications for the C biogeochemical cycle, as
450 reduced N availability constrains plant productivity and weakens its capacity to offset
451 soil C losses. By uncovering these mechanisms, our study highlights how increasing
452 temperatures can drive irreversible C losses in cold ecosystems.

453 *Warming effects on the N stabilization in the non-extractable soil fraction*

454 The non-extractable soil fraction had the greatest influence on total ¹⁵N retention in this
455 subarctic grassland, due to its substantial size relative to other ecosystem pools (Fig. 4).
456 Several mechanisms can contribute to the 1.7-2.6% lower N stabilization within this
457 pool per °C of warming. Some amino acids used for ¹⁵N tracing and naturally present
458 in soil, such as glutamic acid or lysine, contribute to *ex vivo* organic matter stabilization
459 through their dissociable functional groups (Schmidt et al., 2011; Lehmann and Kleber,
460 2015) that form stable bonds with clay minerals and organic matter. Additionally, ¹⁵N-
461 enriched microbial necromass interacts with soil minerals, contributing to *in vivo*
462 stabilization (Cotrufo and Lavelle, 2022; Manzoni and Cotrufo, 2024). The fast
463 assimilation of amino acids by microbial biomass and later bonding of microbially-
464 transformed products to the soil matrix can constitute the most important amino acid
465 stabilization pathway even just few hours after the addition to the soil (Rothstein, 2010;
466 Dippold et al., 2013). Importantly, the ¹⁵N-labeled amino acid mixture used for tracing
467 included several of the most abundant and bioavailable amino acids in high-latitude
468 soils—such as alanine, glycine, glutamate, and aspartate—with a wide range of
469 chemical properties, ensuring that the observed amino acid stabilization patterns reflect
470 ecologically relevant pathways (Weintraub and Schimel, 2005; Andresen et al., 2022;

471 Kielland, 1995). These stabilization processes not only sequester C but also N within
472 the soil matrix, reducing their accessibility to soil microbes and potential losses through
473 mineralization.

474 While reduced background organic matter under warming could theoretically enhance
475 mineral sorption capacity by lowering competition for binding sites (Charles et al.,
476 2008; Kaiser & Guggenberger, 2003), the net effect was a decline in stabilization
477 capacity. This is likely due to the concurrent depletion of microbial biomass,
478 necromass, and sorption-promoting organic ligands, which play a crucial role in both
479 *in vivo* and *ex vivo* N retention (Poepflau et al., 2017; Dwivedi et al., 2019; Liao et al.,
480 2025). Elevated temperatures reduce microbial biomass and necromass production
481 (Fig. 1d, e), limiting the supply of residues essential for *in vivo* stabilization (Allison
482 and Treseder, 2008; Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2018; Walker et al., 2018). At the same
483 time, warming causes the depletion of soil organic compounds (Fig. 1a, b) involved in
484 *ex vivo* N stabilization (Rothstein, 2010; Dwivedi et al., 2019). This dual effect
485 diminishes the soil capacity to stabilize N, increasing the risk of N losses from the
486 ecosystem.

487 *Warming effects on the N retention capacity of fine roots and soil microbial biomass*

488 Fine roots and microbial biomass, although accounting for only 2.1% and 1.5% of the
489 N pools in this subarctic grassland, respectively, stored up to 10.8% and 22.6% of the
490 labeled ¹⁵N during the snowmelt period (Fig. 3). This highlights their critical role as
491 dynamic N reservoirs, rapidly immobilizing N in response to seasonal availability
492 (Clemmensen et al., 2008; Larsen et al., 2012; Xu et al., 2013). Microbial biomass, in
493 particular, has high turnover rates and fast N immobilization, making it a key driver of
494 nutrient fluxes in cold soils (Bardgett et al., 2003; Haugwitz et al., 2011). During
495 thawing events, microbial turnover releases substantial amounts of N into the plant-soil
496 system, providing a vital nutrient source for plants during the growing season (Lipson
497 et al., 2000; Sorensen et al., 2008). Although microbial biomass typically reaches its
498 maximum in late winter and declines steeply during soil thaw (Schnecker et al., 2023),

499 we did not detect this seasonal pattern in the total biomass C and N pools (Fig. 1d, e).
500 However, the highest ^{15}N recovery in microbial biomass was observed during the
501 snowmelt period (Fig. 3), which was associated with a higher N immobilization
502 capacity in this season (Fig. 5 and fig.6b), consistent with its role in regulating N
503 availability according to plant demands (Isobe et al., 2018).

504 The same seasonal trend was also observed with the ^{15}N recovered by fine roots
505 (Fig. 3 and fig. 5). Some plant species in subarctic grasslands, conserve over-wintering
506 green aboveground structures and have adaptations to rapidly absorb N released during
507 thawing events to support early spring growth (Chapin et al., 1986; Starr et al., 2003;
508 Larsen et al., 2012). This interplay between microbial biomass and fine roots highlights
509 their complementary roles in regulating N dynamics in cold ecosystems. By
510 immobilizing N during periods of low plant demand and releasing it when demand
511 peaks, microbial biomass buffer seasonal nutrient fluctuations and sustain ecosystem
512 functioning.

513 However, our results revealed that warming reduces the capacity of microbial
514 biomass and fine roots to temporarily store N during the snowmelt period (Fig. 4), just
515 when this function is more important. This reduction was likely due to a decline in the
516 size of these pools (Fig. 1e and fig. 2b), as indicated by their unaltered ^{15}N enrichment
517 under warming (Fig. 6b, d), suggesting no changes in their physiological N retention
518 capacity. Consistently, fine root biomass and the correspondent C and N pools declined
519 after 11 years of warming in the same subarctic grassland (Bhattarai et al., 2023), which
520 was associated to shifts in plant community composition toward pioneer species like
521 *Equisetum spp.* Moreover, soil N losses under warming have led to reduced fine root
522 production and thinner roots with higher specific root area (Fang et al., 2023),
523 consistent with lower fine root C:N ratios found here (Fig. 2c). Nonetheless, the effects
524 of warming on belowground biomass are complex and can vary across different
525 ecosystems depending on warming magnitude and duration (Wang et al., 2021).

526 Warming also reduced microbial biomass (Fig. 1d, e) due to increased respiratory
527 demands and the subsequent soil C depletion needed for microbial biomass
528 maintenance under chronic warmer temperatures (Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2018;
529 Walker et al., 2018). Strict microbial C:N stoichiometric demands further constrained
530 microbial N retention under chronic warming (Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2019).
531 Consistently, elevated temperatures generally lead to a decrease in microbial N biomass
532 while enhancing N mineralization and nitrification across different ecosystems (Gao
533 and Yan, 2019; Dai et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2024; Tian et al., 2023). Interestingly, Peplau
534 et al (2021) observed that while warming reduced soil C stocks in a subarctic deciduous
535 forest, N was not lost but shifted from particulate organic matter (POM) to mineral-
536 associated organic matter (MAOM), suggesting stabilization of N via microbial
537 necromass incorporation into MAOM. In our study, lower soil C:N ratios (14.01 ± 0.16
538 versus 17.69 ± 1.74 in the topsoils investigated by Peplau et al. (2021)) likely
539 exacerbated microbial C limitation, promoting microbial N mineralization rather than
540 immobilization in microbial biomass and contributing to lower N retention capacity
541 under warming (Wild et al. 2015; Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2019). Therefore,
542 temperature-driven shifts in fine roots and soil microbial biomass compromised the
543 temporal N retention function of these reservoirs during the snowmelt period,
544 contributing to the opening of the N cycle.

545 *Warming-induced shifts in aboveground plant N uptake and allocation*

546 By contrast, warming increased aboveground N uptake during the growing season, as
547 is shown by the positive response of the ^{15}N pool recovered in living aboveground plant
548 tissues (aboveground green vegetation) during summer and spring (Fig. 4). The
549 observed increase in aboveground biomass, resulting in higher C and N stocks (Fig. 2g
550 and h), and the concurrent rise the ^{15}N concentration in aboveground plant tissues (Fig.
551 6e) suggests that warming influenced not only plant growth, but also N assimilation
552 and allocation. These results are consistent with the increase in maximum annual NDVI
553 values at higher soil temperatures found in the same study sites (Mortier et al. 2024).

554 Increased rates of N mineralization and turnover at warmer temperatures can alleviate
555 plant N limitations in cold ecosystems (Turner and Henry, 2010), leading to higher
556 plant N uptake and to shifts towards above-ground plant allocation (Wang et al., 2016).
557 Previous studies demonstrate that plants rely more on free amino acid uptake to support
558 N demands in unfertile soils, as is the case here in warmer soils, and mycorrhizal
559 associations can also influence plant amino acid uptake (Andresen et al., 2022). Indeed,
560 arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal biomass showed a positive response to warming in the
561 same sites (Zhang et al., 2020). Increased plant reliance on associations with arbuscular
562 mycorrhizal fungi would help to explain the observed increases in aboveground
563 vegetation biomass despite reduced soil N stocks and lower root biomass. Shifts on
564 biomass and N allocation of subarctic vegetation towards aboveground parts at warmer
565 conditions could significantly influence C and N cycling by altering the quality,
566 quantity and spatial distribution of litter inputs into the soil.

567 *Warming-induced N imbalances and asynchronies between plant and soil microbial N*
568 *cycling*

569 Warming can therefore alter the subtle balance between microbial N mineralization and
570 plant uptake (Dawes et al., 2017; Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2019), due to both
571 asynchronies and imbalances between these two N fluxes (Lacroix et al. 2022). Despite
572 aboveground vegetation N uptake increased slightly with warming during the growing
573 seasons compensating partially the N loss in the dissolved N fraction (Fig. 4), the
574 magnitude of N released from soil microbial biomass and fine roots in the cold season
575 (1.99% of N lost °C⁻¹) exceeded by far the small increase of the plant N uptake during
576 the growing season (0.14% of N gained °C⁻¹). The asynchrony between the warming
577 induced N flux from the microbial biomass and fine root pools during the snowmelt
578 period and the optimum photoperiod for plant growth may have also prevented
579 vegetation to take much advantage from the extra N released to the soil, limiting the
580 positive response of plant productivity to increasing temperatures (Fang et al., 2023).
581 In addition, soil microbes may have faster response rates and a higher capacity of
582 adaptation to fast temperature increases compared to vegetation or other large

583 organisms with slower turnover rates and generation times, which need longer times to
584 adapt (Classen et al., 2015). These different rates of adaptation could also have
585 contributed to the opening of the N cycle, causing coupled and proportional soil C and
586 N losses (Fig. 1).

587 These results must be interpreted in the context of the specific characteristics of
588 our experimental approach. Geothermal gradients, while primarily heating soils with
589 minimal effect on air temperature (Sigurdsson et al., 2016), offer a unique opportunity
590 to investigate long-term warming effects *in situ*, including extreme warming levels.
591 Although soil and air temperature decoupling may affect some aboveground–
592 belowground interactions differently than in climatic warming (Rustad et al., 2001;
593 Hanson et al., 2017; Bai et al., 2023), the focus on soil processes remains particularly
594 relevant in cold ecosystems, where soil temperature is a dominant control on microbial
595 activity, nutrient cycling, and C stabilization (Ferrari et al., 2018). Furthermore, as in
596 most warming experiments, the abrupt onset of warming may have constrained the
597 adaptive capacity of slow-responding organisms, potentially altering trophic
598 interactions and plant–soil feedbacks (Classen et al., 2015; De Boeck et al., 2015; Yin
599 et al., 2023). Ongoing experiments simulating gradual warming through periodical
600 mesocosm transplantations in these study sites will further refine our understanding of
601 ecosystem vulnerability to realistic warming trajectories.

602 Despite these limitations, the absence of physical disturbance and the stable, and
603 continuous nature of the geothermal gradients—spanning both projected and extreme
604 warming levels—make this system highly suitable for assessing subarctic ecosystem
605 responses to warming. Our results reveal a consistent decline in N retention across
606 major soil pools, with the largest proportional losses occurring in the non-extractable
607 soil fraction, a key reservoir for long-term stabilization. Warming reduced the short-
608 term immobilization of N in soil microbial biomass and fine roots, particularly during
609 the snowmelt period, weakening both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* soil N stabilization pathways.
610 These shifts disrupted the synchrony between plant and microbial N cycling, opening
611 the N cycle and weakening the system’s capacity to conserve N. By revealing how
612 warming destabilizes soil N retention, this study highlights a critical but

613 underappreciated driver of soil C loss and ecosystem vulnerability in a rapidly changing
614 climate.

615

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935

936 **Figures:**

937 Graphical abstract: Schematic representation of the main effects of soil warming on
938 nitrogen (N) retention in ecosystem pools. During the snowmelt period (lower panel),
939 warming reduces soil microbial biomass and fine root biomass, weakening their
940 capacity to temporarily immobilize N. This leads to a decline in the stabilization of N
941 within the non-extractable soil organic matter fraction, increasing overall N losses.
942 During the growing season (upper panel), warming stimulates aboveground plant
943 biomass and N uptake, partially offsetting N losses in the dissolved soil fraction,
944 although plant N uptake is asynchronous and insufficient to counteract the soil N
945 retention declines. These disruptions in N cycling contribute to proportional and
946 probably irreversible soil carbon losses.

947

948 Fig. 1. Effect of soil warming and seasons on a) soil organic C stocks, b) total soil N
949 stocks, c) total soil C:N ratios, d) microbial C stocks, e) microbial N stocks, f)
950 standardized soil, microbial and dissolved C and N stocks, g) dissolved organic C
951 stocks, h) total dissolved N stocks, and i) C:N ratios in dissolved and microbial
952 fractions. *P* values indicate the effect of warming, season and their interaction
953 according to linear models on previously transformed variables. Lines indicate
954 significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of warming. Shadowed areas around lines represent the
955 confidence intervals of the regressions. Box plots indicate significant ($P < 0.05$) effect
956 of seasons only. Different letters indicate significant differences among seasons within
957 each pool according to post-hoc Sidak corrections for multiple comparisons. Asterisks
958 indicate significant differences between pools within seasons.

959

960 Fig. 2. Effect of soil warming and seasons on a) C stocks, b) N stocks, and c) C:N ratios
961 in fine roots, d) C stocks, e) N stocks, and f) C:N ratios in coarse roots and rhizomes,
962 g) C stocks and h) N stocks in green aboveground vegetation, and i) standardized soil
963 and root C and N stocks. *P* values indicate the effect of warming, season and their
964 interaction according to linear models on previously transformed variables. Lines

965 indicate significant ($P<0.05$) effect of warming. Shadowed areas around lines represent
966 the confidence intervals of the regressions. Box plots indicate significant ($P<0.05$)
967 effect of season only. Different letters indicate significant differences among seasons
968 according to post-hoc Sidak corrections for multiple comparisons.

969

970 Fig. 3. Percentage of the ^{15}N pool recovered in the different ecosystem pools of ambient
971 temperature plots two weeks after tracing with ^{15}N amino acids. Bars represent averages
972 of ambient temperature plots per ecosystem pool and season ($n=5$). Error bars represent
973 the standard errors. Letters indicate significant differences of each pool among seasons
974 according to one-way ANOVAs ($P<0.05$), where different letters indicate significant
975 differences among seasons according to post-hoc Sidak corrections for multiple
976 comparisons.

977

978 Fig. 4. Effect of soil warming on the ^{15}N recovered in the different ecosystem pools
979 across seasons. Bright or intense colors indicate statistically significant effects of
980 warming on ^{15}N retention according to lineal models for each ecosystem pool and
981 season ($n=20$), as shown by the accompanying P-values ($P < 0.05$). Pale tones indicate
982 non-significant responses.

983

984 Fig. 5. Comparison of the ^{15}N enrichment in the different ecosystem pools two weeks
985 after tracing with ^{15}N amino acids. Bars represent averages per ecosystem pool and
986 season ($n=20$). Error bars represent the standard errors.

987

988 Fig. 6. Effect of soil warming and seasons on the ^{15}N enrichment in a) bulk soil, b)
989 microbial biomass, and c) dissolved soil fraction, d) fine roots, e) green aboveground
990 vegetation, and f) senescent aboveground vegetation. P values indicate the effect of
991 warming, season and their interaction according to linear models on previously
992 transformed variables. Box plots indicate significant ($P<0.05$) effect of season only.
993 Lines indicate significant ($P<0.05$) effect of warming. Shadowed areas around lines
994 represent the confidence intervals of the regressions. Different letters indicate

995 significant differences among seasons according to post-hoc Sidak corrections for
996 multiple comparisons.

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